

**DEBRECENI
EGYETEM**

Book of Abstracts

Absztrakt kötet

**CONFERENCE ON THERAPEUTICAL
PURPOSES RESEARCH AND
DEVELOPMENT III.**

**III. TERÁPIÁS CÉLÚ KUTATÁSOK ÉS FEJLESZTÉSEK
KONFERENCIA**

Book of abstracts:

Conference on Therapeutical Purposes Research and Development III.

Szerkesztők:

Prof. Dr. Bácskay Ildikó

Dr. Józsa Liza

Dr. Vasvári Gábor

Dr. Nemes Dániel

Dr. Haimhoffer Ádám

ISBN 978-963-490-498-4

Welcome Remark

Dear Colleagues,

Welcome to the 3rd hybrid Conference on Therapeutic Purposes Research and Development. Taking place on February 2-3, 2023. in Debrecen, Hungary. The Conference aims to summarize the results of the project called R&D for Therapeutic. The purpose of the conference is to get to know the latest results of different research fields, to get information, to ask questions and to share opinions. In addition, the conference provides an opportunity to present the results of various domestic and international R&D projects. We also provide young researchers, PhD and undergraduate students with the opportunity to present their work.

Sincerely Yours,

The Organizing Committee

Köszöntő

Kedves Kollégák!

Üdvözljük önöket a 3. alkalommal hibrid módon megrendezett Terápiás célú kutatások és fejlesztések konferencián, mely 2023. február 2-3-án kerül megrendezésre Debrecenben. A konferencia célja, hogy a hallgatóság bepillantást nyerjen az eltérő kutatási területek legújabb eredményeibe, tájékozódjon, feltehesse kérdéseit, ütköztethesse véleményét. Emellett a konferencia lehetőséget ad a különböző hazai és nemzetközi K+F célú projektek eredményeinek megismerésére, bemutatására. A fiatal kutatóknak, PhD és TDK hallgatóknak is lehetőséget biztosítunk, hogy bemutassák munkájukat.

Tisztelettel,

A Szervező Bizottság

Influence of probiotics and bile acids on the gliclazide permeation: in vitro PAMPA model study

Nebojša Pavlović¹, Maja Đanić², Bojan Stanimirov³, Slavica Lazarević², Saša Vukmirović², Hani Al-Salami⁴, Momir Mikov²

¹Department of Pharmacy, Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Hajduk Veljkova 3, Novi Sad, Vojvodina, Serbia

²Department of Pharmacology, Toxicology and Clinical Pharmacology, Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Hajduk Veljkova 3, Novi Sad, Vojvodina, Serbia

³Department of Biochemistry, Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Hajduk Veljkova 3, Novi Sad, Vojvodina, Serbia

⁴School of Pharmacy and Biomedical Sciences, Curtin Health Innovation Research Institute, Curtin University, B305 Kent St, Bentley WA 6102, Perth, Australia

Gliclazide is a drug characterized by large inter-individual differences in therapeutic response, but the causes of these differences are not fully explained [1]. Gut microbiota and bile acids are known to possess the ability to modify absorption and pharmacokinetic profiles of many drugs [2]. The aim of this work was to determine the effects of probiotic bacteria and bile acids on the gliclazide permeability. The permeability of gliclazide, with and without probiotic bacteria and bile acids (cholic acid, CA and deoxycholic acid, DCA), was tested using in vitro PAMPA intestinal model at pH 5.8-7.4. Concentrations of gliclazide were determined by HPLC analysis. Besides, probiotics were incubated with gliclazide in order to investigate the bacterial accumulation of gliclazide. The interactions of gliclazide and bile acids were investigated by molecular mechanics (MM2) calculations. Probiotics significantly increased the permeability of gliclazide across the PAMPA membrane at all observed pH values, while the total amount of gliclazide during incubation with bacteria was significantly reduced at pH 7.4, which could be a result of the drug metabolism by bacterial enzymes. During the 24 h incubation with probiotics, significantly lower extracellular concentrations of gliclazide were observed at each time point compared to controls. Bile acids, particularly DCA, decreased the permeability of gliclazide through PAMPA membrane, which can be explained by forming stable gliclazide/DCA complexes. Given that probiotic bacteria and bile acids are naturally present in the gut and that each individual has a specific bacterial fingerprint, future research should focus on the gliclazide therapy individualization using in vivo models.

This research was funded by the Provincial Secretariat for Higher Education and Science of Vojvodina (project No. 142-451-3179/2022-01).

References

1. Đanić, M. et al. *Front. Pharmacol.* 10, 1083 (2019)
2. Pavlović, N. et al. *Front. Pharmacol.* 9, 1283 (2018)